

CSI Forensics Workshop

INTRODUCTION

The word *forensic* means "pertaining to the courts of law," and thus forensic science means science applied to legal matters. Forensic science not only covers criminal and civil courts, but also quasi-judicial processes such as insurance claims.

In 1910, Frenchman Edmund Locard founded a small police laboratory dedicated to forensic science. Locard was the first to put forward the theory that a criminal almost always leaves behind a physical clue at the scene of a crime - a fibre, a fingerprint, a bullet - all of which are vital pointers to the criminal's identity.

POSSIBLE ACTIVITIES:

Fingerprinting: Use graphite powder, iodine crystals, gentian violet techniques

Plaster casts: mould of bite taken from apple

Digital photography: Crime scene, fingerprint results, DNA fingerprint results

Blood splatter analysis: Sheep blood or red food colouring

Blood typing: Blood type antigens and agglutination

Blood detection: Luminol, use hypochlorite for fake blood

Hair and fibres analysis: Use microscopes and prepared standard slides.

Molecular fingerprinting: Electrophoresis "DNA" demo

Refractive index: Chart of RI values & lab report of RI of glass from suspect & scene

Water/Soil ions testing: simple Cl^- , Fe^{+2} , Fe^{+3} , Cu^{+2} testing (use Silver Nitrate for Chloride ions and Sodium Hydroxide for metal ions. Provide standard test solutions)

New Plymouth CIB: Presentation to students and crime scene setup.

ROOMS/EQUIPMENT:

- Computer suite for internet forensics lesson
- Laboratory for microscopes and electrophoresis, lab for blood typing and everything else.
- Microscope hooked into TV for fibre and hair matching
- Data projector, digital camera, floppy disks (at least 1 per team: 6), laptop
- Tower A, Level 3 top corridor for crime scene. Nice and dark for luminol test.
- Lab coats, safety glasses and gloves for students (24 max students + 3 supervisors)
- Evidence collection kits (plastic bags, marker pens, stickers, tweezers)
- Electrophoresis chambers, power packs, blue tops, digital balances, autopipettes and ARTs
- Paper for blood splatter analysis, pasteur pipettes and bulbs
- Stock solutions for ion testing, test-tubes, droppers
- Ice-cream containers to make plaster of paris, cardboard for moulds around tyre or shoe tracks
- Spray bottle of Luminol
- Broken glass for crime scene with culprit fingerprint planted. One piece per team (6) with anyone else also present.
- Dog hair, cloth fragments
- Childs poster paint for shoeprints, lots of computer paper

POSSIBLE CRIME SCENE:

Tower A, Level 3: Use chalk outline of victim. Use Police Tape to cordon off area. Place shoe/boot prints, handprints, etc, using hypochlorite for fake blood. Allow to dry. Plant hair or clothing fibres, broken glass (one large piece with culprits fingerprint on it and one other persons)

CRIME SCENE EVIDENCE

Personnel	Evidence
The victim <i>DEPENDS ON NP CIB ASSISTANCE!</i>	Chalk outline showing body position. Blood obvious (sheep blood); splatter (measure width for use later to determine height fallen). Victim blood as partial culprit shoeprint undetectable unless using luminol. Broken glass, large fragment has prints to detect. Cellotape with print on it. Hair (from culprit and unknowns), fibres. White powder (Iron II Chloride or similar).
The culprit	Cut finger with elastoplast on it. Footprint found at scene matches his shoeprint. Gives reason to detect blood on shoe and any others with same tread pattern (found with luminol). Culprit fingerprint on glass fragment found at scene, hair of culprit at scene and unknown hair and fibres
The rest of the class	All (including tutors and demonstrator/culprit) determine own blood type, fingerprint, shoeprint, hair as part of teaching sequence but records kept.

<i>Evidence linked to culprit:</i>
Shoeprint
Blood type (tell students blood found at scene tested for them is ... (matches culprit))
Hair
Fingerprint on broken glass
Cut finger with elastoplast on it.
Drops of blood prepared for electrophoresis

<i>Evidence to distract:</i>
Broken glass of various types (broken Pasteur pipettes, conical flask or test tube), other fingerprint on large broken glass and on cellotape.
Sheep blood, spilt from height (around 1m)
Dog hair, clothing fibres
White powder (Iron III Chloride or Iron II Chloride)

PLANNING TIMELINE

Date	Activity	Time Period
Dec. 11 (Dec 16) 9:30 am	Welcome, workshop outline, introduction (PowerPoint). Divide students into teams of 4 (6 teams of 4 = 24 students) Assign Forensic Team responsibilities. Leader assigns other duties	10 minutes
	Guest speaker : Detective Senior Seargent Grant Coward, New Plymouth CIB	2 hour block period
	Police fingerprinting (in lab) and evidence collection from Crime Scene in A111 (Scene Of Crime Officer , Constable)	Teams have 20 minutes to investigate CS.
LUNCH 12:30 pm to 1: 30pm	LUNCH	LUNCH
	What is Forensics, CS defn, evidence collection (PowerPoint)	20 minutes
	Blood splatter analysis, fingerprints from morning placed on corridor wall for mass viewing. Clean up. Summary/questions. Details of Day 2 and Day 3 activities.	35 minutes
END DAY 1 3:00pm	END DAY 1 Take computer disks with photos for printing...	END DAY 1
Dec 12 (Dec 17) 9:30am	Recap Day 1; work in same roles as Day 1 What do terms mean? CS, etc. Evidence analysis in laboratory PowerPoint for blood, hair/fibres	30 minutes
	Round-robin of activities	1 hour
TEA BREAK		10 minutes
	Discuss findings (update corridor wall) Look at printed photos	20 minutes
LUNCH 12:00 to 1:00pm	LUNCH	LUNCH
	DNA fingerprinting practice	2 hours
END DAY 2 3:00pm	END DAY 2	END DAY 2

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Dec 13 (Dec 18)	Evidence analysis in laboratory DNA fingerprint/electrophoresis	2 hours
LUNCH	LUNCH	LUNCH
	Final report	½ hour
	Computer suite Evaluation sheets CLASS PHOTO	1 ½ hours
END DAY 3	END DAY 3	END DAY 3

FORENSIC TEAM RESPONSIBILITIES

Chief of Forensics

In charge of entire investigation. Responsible in proper handling of evidence and forensic laboratory examinations. Ultimately responsible for the accuracy of the final Forensic Report.

Investigative Reporter

Primary responsibility is to prepare a written Forensic Report after reviewing the evidence, preliminary police report, and collaborating with other Forensic Team members.

Evidence Recorder

Responsible for obtaining the evidence from the scene, making sure it is handled properly. In addition all evidence must be properly observed and diagramed/logged onto a Forensic Laboratory Evidence Sheet.

Forensic Photographer/Documentation

This person will photograph the scene and evidence. Thorough documentation includes a full sketch of the crime scene as well as an additional sketches of pertinent evidence. In addition to sketches, the photographer will utilise a digital camera to photograph and digitise the scene and laboratory results where appropriate.

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BLOODSTAIN PATTERN ANALYSIS

What may Bloodstain Pattern Analysis do for your case?

BPA (Bloodstain Pattern Analysis) may on many occasions, clearly define the location of the victim or the assailant(s) by establishing the actions of either or both. Possible and impossible scenarios may be established to determine if the victim/witness/assailant is accurately describing what took place.

- What type of weapon or impact occurred to cause the bloodstains present?
- How many times was the victim struck ?
- Where was the victim(s) at the time the injuries were inflicted?
- Where was the assailant(s) during and following the assault?
- Is the bloodstain evidence consistent with the medical examiner findings?
- Is the bloodstain evidence on the suspect and his/her clothing consistent with the crime scene?

Blood Splatter Lab

Problem: How does changing the distance effect how a drop of blood falls?

Hypothesis:

Materials: Artificial blood Dropper 50 ml beaker Paper Ruler Meter ruler

Procedure:

1. Put the dropper 10 cm above paper and drop one drop of blood. Be careful you do not get blood on the floor, table or your clothing.
2. Measure the diameter of the splatter in centimetres. Write it down in the observation table.
3. Repeat this process with 20cm to 200 cm. For greater heights you may need to stand on a table or chair and use newspaper to prevent accidents.
4. Get an unknown splatter from your supervisor. Measure it and see if you can determine how far the blood dropped.

Observations:

Questions:

1. What is the effect of the different heights on the diameter of the spot?
2. Diameter of the mystery splatter = _____cm
3. How far do you think your mystery splatter dropped?
4. What other methods may be utilised to establish blood patterns found?
5. What is the importance of preserving and analysing blood as evidence?

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DETECTING LATENT BLOOD

In forensic investigations, especially in cases of murder, it is sometimes necessary to employ a method for the detection of blood which is hidden from the naked eye. Luminol produces a reaction which is extremely sensitive, capable of detecting bloodstains diluted up to 10,000 times, through the emission of light known as luminescence. Once the crime scene is secured and all physical evidence is obtained, the forensic scientist can spray the luminol reagent onto a variety of surfaces to detect trace evidence that would have otherwise gone unnoticed. Luminol has proven to be effective on a variety of surfaces: walls, carpets, household and industrial furniture, and even the interior, exterior and trunks of vehicles used to dispose of a victim.

One of the important presumptive tests to identify blood is the luminol test. Unlike some of the other tests, the reaction of blood with luminol results in the production of light rather than colour. By spraying luminol reagent onto a suspect item, large areas can be quickly screened for the presence of bloodstains. The sprayed objects must be located in a darkened area while being viewed for the emission of light (luminescence).

The luminol reacts with the hemoglobin in the blood. Since it is difficult to break down hemoglobin, this test can be done many months after a crime has been committed, even if the blood has been cleaned up.

Materials:

- Luminol reagent 0.1g
- Sodium carbonate 5.0 g
- 100 ml distilled water
- 0.7 g of sodium perborate
- Household bleach – diluted to 10 ml per 100 ml of water (simulated blood)

Procedure:

1. Mix 5.0 g of sodium carbonate in 100 ml of distilled water
2. Add into the above 0.1 g of luminol reagent
3. Before use, add 0.7 g of sodium perborate into the solution
4. Put the mixture into a spray bottle
5. Prepare another spray bottle with the bleach mixture
6. Tape filter paper on the walls or front blackboard
7. Darken the room
8. Spray the bleach solution onto the filter paper
9. Immediately spray the luminol onto the bleach
10. The mixtures react to produce a blue glow (luminescence)

(Mixing the two solutions into a test tube can also show this process.)

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DNA FINGERPRINT ANALYSIS

What may DNA fingerprint analysis do for your case?

No two people have the same genetic fingerprint (*unless* they are identical twins or clones!)

Media:

2% AGAROSE gel:

In 100 ml deionised water:

2 g agarose
0.8 g baking soda

0.8% Sodium Carbonate (Baking Soda) buffer:

In 200 ml deionised water:

1.6 g baking soda

Method:

1. Place in 250ml Blue Top and heat in microwave for 1 minute on high.
2. Swirl contents (CARE! HOT!) and continue heating for 15 second bursts with appropriate careful swirling to dissolve.
3. Allow to cool for 10 minutes on the bench, swirling after 5 minutes.
4. If the agarose is not completely dissolved repeat 15 second burst of heat in the microwave until no agarose threads are visible.
5. Once adequately dissolved, cool under running cold water (swirling contents continuously) to hand heat.
6. Place the casting tray and dams into the Horizon electrophoresis chamber.
7. Use a blue tip to seal the edges of the casting tray with the dams on either using a little of the cool agarose.
8. Leave to set for 2 minutes.
9. Insert the 12 tooth comb at the black negative terminal end of the tray and pour a 3 or 4 mm thick gel.
10. Allow to set for 20 minutes. Prepare samples while you wait.

Sample preparation

For food colouring, flower petal pigment or marker pen ink, take 2-5 μ l and add to equal volume of glycerol (glycerine), mixing well.

For Harrison dyes (A, B, C and D) no glycerol is required.

Loading and running the gel:

Flood the gel with buffer to a depth of 2mm above the surface of the gel. Ensure all wells are full and no air bubbles are present. Use ART's to load only 2-5 μ l of sample to a well. Run at 70mA, 250-300V for about 1½ hours.

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FINGERPRINT ANALYSIS

What may fingerprint analysis do for your case?

No two people have the same fingerprint, *not even* identical twins! Fingerprints are sorted into 3 types of prints: **arch**, **loop** and **whorl**. Fingerprints form when the ridges of your skin leave a mark on objects you touch. Sweat glands release water, salt and urea while the sebaceous glands release oil onto the surface of your skin. Fine dark powder is used to show up fingerprints on light, smooth surfaces and fine white powder is used to show up fingerprints on dark, smooth surfaces.

Simple Fingerprinting:

Equipment: The equipment includes...

- spatula;
- sheet of newspaper;
- carbon powder;
- soft brush;
- glossy paper, filter paper, black plastic, cloth.

Background knowledge: Filter paper and cloth will not create a good fingerprint. Fingerprinting is only good on some surfaces. You can investigate this with your class. A similar thing can be done using white powder on the same surfaces.

Method: Lay a sheet of newspaper on a table. Put one of the sample paper or cloth on the newspaper and press your finger into it to make a fingerprint. Sprinkle a very small amount of carbon powder onto the reverse side where the fingerprint is. Gently brush away any carbon powder. Try some of the other samples.

Fingerprinting from sticky surfaces:

Equipment: The equipment includes...

- stick tape;
- gentian violet;
- 250mL beaker;
- tweezers;
- glass rod;
- scissors.

Background knowledge: Gentian violet, mixed with phenol and alcohol, can be used to show up fingerprints on sticky surfaces. The phenol, which is an acid, takes away the stickiness and the fingerprint is stained a deep purple colour by the gentian violet.

Method: Cut a piece of sticky tape and stick it to a glass rod (like a flag exposing some of the sticky side to the tape). Press your finger into the sticky tape near the end. Carefully pour 100mL of gentian violet into the beaker and then lower the sticky tape into the beaker solution. After 15 minutes lift the glass rod from the beaker and run the sticky tape under water thoroughly to remove the stickiness. The fingerprint should now be visible.

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Fingerprinting from rough surfaces:

Equipment: The equipment includes...

- screw jar containing iodine crystals;
- filter paper;
- clear tape;
- tweezers.

Background knowledge: Iodine crystals are used to show up fingerprints on rough, absorbent surfaces. These crystals give off iodine vapour which dissolves on the tiny drops of oil in the fingerprint. The fingerprint then shows up more clearly.

Method: Press your finger on to a piece of filter paper. Put the filter paper into the jar of iodine crystals and screw the top on. When you can see the fingerprint clearly, remove the paper using the tweezers. Cover the fingerprint on both sides with clear tape. Repeat this procedure with another piece of filter paper but this time do **not** cover it with clear tape.

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PLASTER CASTS

What may plaster casts analysis do for your case?

Making a plaster cast:

Equipment: The equipment includes...

- plastic beaker;
- water;
- plaster of Paris;
- plastic stirrer;
- measuring cylinder;
- brush.

Background knowledge: Marks such as shoeprints are often left at the scene of a crime. These can become important clues and evidence against a perpetrator can be found. Police often use plaster of Paris to make casts.

Method: Put about 70mL of water in the plastic beaker. Fill the **dry** glass beaker with plaster of Paris. Pour the plaster into the water and stir well until you have a thick, smooth cream. Pour it into the mould quickly and let it set for about 24 hours. Lift off the cast and rinse the cast under the tap and brush if necessary.

- Why is it important to wash the plaster cast before examining?
- What effect does air bubbles in the plaster have on the cast?

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CHEMICAL ION ANALYSIS

What may ion analysis do for your case?

Simple Chemical Ion Detection:

Equipment: The equipment includes...

- Test-tubes;
- Silver Nitrate solution
- Sodium Hydroxide solution;
- Droppers;
- Standard solutions containing Cl^- , Fe^{+2} , Fe^{+3} , Cu^{+2} and Al^{+3} ions.

Background knowledge: Chloride ions can be detected with Silver Nitrate solution - a white ppt forms. Normal tap water (and swimming pool water) is chlorinated to kill germs. Seawater contains sea salt – sodium chloride. River water contains virtually no chloride ions. To detect metal ions we use Sodium Hydroxide. A coloured ppt often forms, its colour is the clue to the identity of the metal ion present.

Method: Add 5mls of a test solution to a clean test tube:

TO TEST FOR CHLORIDE ANION: Add a few drops of Silver Nitrate solution; a cloudy ppt is positive

TO TEST FOR CATIONS: Add a few drops of Sodium hydroxide solution

Cu^{+2} - blue ppt; Fe^{+2} - green ppt Fe^{+3} - rust red ppt Al^{+3} ions - white ppt dissolves in xs

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HAIR/FIBRE ANALYSIS

What may hair/fibre analysis do for your case?

Hairs, which are composed primarily of the protein keratin, can be defined as slender outgrowths of the skin of mammals. Each species of animal possesses hair with characteristic length, color, shape, root appearance, and internal microscopic features that distinguish one animal from another. Considerable variability also exists in the types of hairs that are found on the body of an animal. In humans, hairs found on the head, pubic region, arms, legs, and other body areas have characteristics that can determine their origin. On animals, hair types include coarse outer hairs or guard hairs, the finer fur hairs, tactile hairs such as whiskers, and other hairs that originate from the tail and mane of an animal.

Because hairs can be transferred during physical contact, their presence can associate a suspect to a victim or a suspect/victim to a crime scene. The types of hair recovered and the condition and number of hairs found all impact on their value as evidence in a criminal investigation. Comparison of the microscopic characteristics of questioned hairs to known hair samples helps determine whether a transfer may have occurred. Crimes such as burglary and armed robbery typically involve the recovery of debris and articles of clothing which may contain hairs useful for the identification of suspects.

There are many factors that impact on the reliability of a hair association, including experience, training, suitability of known hair standards, and adequacy of equipment. Hair associations are strengthened by other pieces of evidence such as DNA fingerprinting.

Simple Hair/Fibre Comparison:

The comparison microscope consists of two compound light microscopes connected by an optical bridge that allows for the simultaneous viewing of questioned hairs and known hairs. Typically, a glass microscope slide containing known or reference hairs is positioned on the stage of one microscope, and a glass microscope slide containing a questioned hair or hairs is positioned on the stage of the other microscope. This enables the hair examiner to compare the microscopic characteristics of the known and questioned hairs in one field. The range of magnification used is approximately 40X to 400X.

Equipment: The equipment includes...

- Microscope;
- Standard prepared slides of common fibres
- Various common animal and human hairs

Method: Place a fibre or hair onto a microscop slide and secure under a coverslip. Examine and draw what you see first at 40X then at 400X. Compare to the reference slides provided to identify the hair/fibres found at the crime scene.